

COMMUNICATION PROBLEMS OF PRESCHOOLERS WITH SYSTEMIC SPEECH UNDERDEVELOPMENT

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Abstract. The article deals with the problems of communication of preschoolers with systemic speech underdevelopment, as well as ways of corrective influence on its development and improvement in children with general speech underdevelopment.

Key words: speech underdevelopment, verbal communication, intelligibility, dialogical speech, monologue speech.

ПРОБЛЕМЫ ОБЩЕНИЯ ДОШКОЛЬНИКОВ С СИСТЕМНЫМ НЕДОРАЗВИТИЕМ РЕЧИ.

Аннотация. В статье рассматриваются проблемы коммуникации дошкольников с системным недоразвитием речи, а также пути коррекционного воздействия по его развитию и совершенствованию у детей с общим недоразвитием речи.

Ключевые слова: недоразвитие речи, речевое общение, внятность, диалогический речь, монологический речь.

The main goal of all reforms carried out in Uzbekistan is to lay a solid foundation for the future of our country. This foundation is created as a result of upbringing healthy, mature and harmoniously developed individuals.

Therefore, our republic has created regulatory documents and a material and technical base aimed at raising the quality of educational work in preschool educational institutions to a new level, expanding the state and non-state network of such organizations, expanding the scale of attracting children with developmental disabilities to inclusive education, providing opportunities for the socialization of children, their all-round development and a radical improvement in the quality of preparation for school.

In the “Action Strategy for Five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021 years”, such tasks as “ ... expansion of the network of preschool educational institutions and dramatic improvement in data conditions institutions for a comprehensive intellectual, aesthetic and physical development of children, ensuring accessibility and significant increasing the coverage of children with preschool education, increasing the level qualifications of teachers and specialists ”. As a result, broad opportunities for the development of speech in preschool children, as well as ensuring a successful transition to the next stage of education.

The formation of communication skills in children with systemic speech underdevelopment for successful socialization in society is one of the priority tasks of special education.

In modern speech therapy, systemic speech underdevelopment is understood as such a deviation in speech development, which is simultaneously characterized by an unformed speaking process and an unformed process of perception of speech messages. "The speech inconsistency of children is manifested both in the impossibility of operating with linguistic means of

communication (phonetic, lexical and grammatical), and in clearly expressed deficiencies in perception, decoding of speech"

Verbal communication is the leading type of human activity, which is an important condition for the full-fledged speech and mental development of a child, the fact of the formation of his personality. Communication is present in all activities of the child. The development and restructuring of the child's mental processes occurs in the form of the appropriation of the social and historical experience of mankind on the basis of communication.

One of the components of verbal communication is the communicative component. In almost any life situation, a person's success is largely associated with the development of his communication skills. These skills determine both the effectiveness of activities and personal relationships. The ability to enter into a dialogue, express your point of view, listen to and hear the opinion of the interlocutor - these abilities need to be developed in children at preschool age.

The main means of communication is speech. Communication skills in children are directly related to the general level of speech development. The development of speech is carried out in close connection with the mental life of the individual. The child's communicative intentions strongly depend on the comfort of communication with a specific interlocutor, on the positive emotional coloring of the contact.

More often preschoolers with speech disorders are inactive, tense, constrained, do not seek to communicate with their peers. The possibilities for the implementation of communications depend on the language means that the child owns, namely on the quality of the lexical, grammatical and phonetic means of the language that the child owns. One of the most typical and persistent manifestations of speech underdevelopment is the insufficiency and inferiority of the lexical side of speech.

The mastery of communication techniques in children with speech disorders occurs later than in children without speech pathologies. An important aspect of interpersonal interaction is the ability to choose adequate ways of communication. These children may be haunted by communicative failures in the process of their verbal interaction, both with adults and with peers.

Studies confirm the presence of interpersonal difficulties in children of this category, due to a low level of intelligibility of oral speech. "Intelligibility" is a universal term that includes intelligibility, on the one hand, and intelligibility, on the other. Intelligibility has a wide meaning, often acting as a substitute for concepts: sufficiently intelligible speech, sufficiently intelligible speech.

The concept of intelligibility is multifaceted, its components are the phonemic intelligibility of the spoken material, and the observance of verbal, logical stress, and the rhythmic-intonational design of the utterance. The correctness of the phonetic composition of words, the correctness of the verbal stress, the correctness of the rhythmic and melodic design of speech are one of the conditions for the communicative success of children with systemic speech underdevelopment

Thus, children with systemic speech underdevelopment are characterized by violations of the lexical-grammatical, phonetic-phonemic and conceptual structure of speech, a paucity of vocabulary, agrammatisms, difficulties in the formation of coherent speech, a decrease in the need for communication.

All this leads to a delay in the development of the communication skills of preschoolers, to the lack of formation of communication methods, a low level of development of dialogic and monologue speech. In this regard, the problem of developing effective ways and methods of forming the means and methods of verbal communication in preschoolers with systemic speech underdevelopment is of particular relevance.

REFERENCES

1. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президентининг 2017 йил 7 февралдаги ПФ-4947-сонли “Ўзбекистон Республикасини янада ривожлантириш бўйича Ҳаракатлар стратегияси тўғрисида” фармони. 14-б. <https://lex.uz/pdfs/3107036>
2. Logopediya: darslik/ M.Y. Ayupova; O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy va o‘rta maxsus ta’lim vazirligi. –T.: O‘zbekiston faylasuflari milliy jamiyati nashriyoti, 2007. -560 b.
3. Воробьева В.К. Методика развития связной речи у детей с системным недоразвитием речи: учебное пособие. – М., 2007. – С. 158.